

1 **General homeobox mobilization during lineage commitment to the trophectoderm in the human**
2 **embryo.**

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7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here the discovery of a
9 group of homeobox transcription factors with function in lineage commitment in embryonic stem cells of
10 the human embryo. Homeobox mobilization featured signature changes in expression of major
11 developmental homeotic factors including Isl1, Zhx3, and Tshz1.

12 Citations

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